

RESEARCH PAPER

SUSTAINABLE ENERGY

Pollution caused from Renewable Energy Construction

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Environmental Pollution from Constructing Renewable Energy Projects

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Index Terms—Sustainable Energy, Environmental Pollution, Habitat Disruption, Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs), Regulatory Measures for Renewable Energy, Alternative Construction Materials

Abstract—This research paper conducts an in-depth analysis of how pollution is caused when moving towards better renewable energy projects. This paper tells us what the implications are and how we can avoid it. The paper delves into many questions but the major question is "What measures should renewable energy generator companies take to minimize pollution during the manufacturing of their projects?" For instance, producing self-driving car batteries involves mining lithium, which significantly contributes to pollution. Similarly, renewable energy projects can also have environmental impacts during their manufacturing processes. What steps can these companies implement to reduce such pollution? This research paper concludes that companies should not rush into any renewable energy project which can cause even more significant damage to our planet. This paper aims to find steps and solutions to these problems, so humanity can go into a better future.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In this technology-driven, modern world, there has been a global shift in the energy sector that is from using fossil fuels and nuclear energy to using the power of the sun, wind, and earth to extract energy. While these renewable energy sources do provide clean and sustainable power, they also cause huge pollution to the earth that can lead to long-term effects. However, the operational phase of this energy is often recognized for the low emission of harmful things but the construction phase has devastating impacts on the environment.

The reliance on non-renewable energy sources like coal, oil, and natural gases has dominated the global energy landscape for over a century. These fossil fuels are also referred to as the backbone of the economic growth of a country. These fossil fuels can lead to many more problems than renewable energies like global warming and climate change. Furthermore, these sources are finite, so the environmental and economic costs of extraction increase day by day.

The construction of renewable energy infrastructure that includes solar farms, windmills, and geothermal plants, involves a huge material extraction, transportation, and establishment processes. These activities are the major cause of environmental pollution. It can also cause many natural disasters like earthquakes from geothermal plants and many more. Also, the mining of rare minerals like lithium, copper, iron, etc from the earth can cause harmful and toxic gases to be liberated into the surrounding ecosystems. Similarly, the making of large solar farms and wind turbines can cause land degradation as it requires a large amount of land. Despite the critical importance of understanding and mitigating these impacts, the construction of renewable energy projects is going unnoticed by the people. They are just focusing on the operational phase, and no one seems to be looking at the facts of construction. This paper gives attention to this gap by exploring the various ways renewable energy projects are contributing to pollution.

This paper will begin by addressing the issues faced by 3 major renewable energy production that are solar panels, geothermal plants, and lithium battery mining. Then we are also going to focus on how these problems can be diminished by using various ways of methods and collaborations. Also, we would go into the theoretical framework that would describe how this solution can help society. Finally, the paper will propose future research directions and policy recommendations aimed at reducing the environmental degradation of renewable energy, ensuring that the transition towards a sustainable energy future is truly beneficial for both people and the planet.

II. PRESENTATION OF THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In recent years, renewable energy generation has grown drastically. Many companies have been built up and many more would be built so there is a need for better planning by these companies to sustain our environment by causing less pollution. Currently, there are many questions to be presented for a better future. This paper delves into how companies can make their production to cause less pollution to the environment. This paper has divided questions based on different industries and how they can improve the conditions of their work.

- a) **Solar Energy Industry:** Solar energy is the most widely used type of renewable energy. Solar energy is radiant light and heat from the Sun that is harnessed using a range of technologies such as solar power to generate electricity, solar thermal energy (including solar water heating), and solar architecture. A major controversial

Fig. 1. Solar Panels [?]

question that could be asked for this paper would be **”What measures are companies taking to manage and mitigate the hazardous waste produced by expired solar cells?”**. This question delves into how solar cells should be treated when they are expired because throwing them away could lead to various types of pollution which is indeed harmful to the environment. There is also a problem in the installation of these panels, we need a large area where sufficient sunlight can fall. [?] Also, the cost of repair and installation is extremely high. So, we need to find solutions to these major problems for a better future. [?]

- b) **Geothermal Energy Industry:** Geothermal Energy is one of the most flexible and clean renewable energy. It is the heat energy from the earth—Geo (earth) + thermal (heat). It is used widely in almost all parts of the world [?]. It is flexible so it can be run 24/7. These are power plants and heat pumps that are installed such that energy is cultivated and used effectively. A huge question that is created is **”With the increasing demand for geothermal plants and heat pumps, there has been a notable rise in induced seismicity. What measures are being implemented to mitigate the risks and impact of these earthquakes, ensuring the sustainable development of geothermal energy?”**. This question delves into how to reduce the risks of more earthquakes caused by installing more power plants. If there is no decrease in these installations, who would be responsible for the destruction caused by these earthquakes? [?]
- c) **Mining and Metals Industry:** Mining and Metals Industry is growing day by day. It is useful in many ways by mining minerals and metals from Earth. These metals and minerals are used in many ways like in Electric Vehicles(EVs), construction, agriculture, etc [?]. These metals are usually lithium, copper, iron, and many more. A

Materials throughput by type of energy source

Fig. 2. Waste Caused

major controversial question to ask is **”How has lithium mining contributed to environmental degradation, specifically through water depletion, drought, and negative impacts on agriculture, and what sustainable practices can mitigate these effects?”**. This question explains to us how lithium mining affects the environment by causing many disasters. If there are no changes made to these activities, in coming years, the Earth is going to be affected very badly [?].

III. METHODS TO TACKLE RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To address the research question addressing the concerns of environmental pollution caused by new, growing renewable energy projects, we have to various steps that help our future generations to get a better life on this Earth. These various steps not only help future generations but also keep in mind about current generations living on Earth. Some of many steps are as follows:

- a) **Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR):** It is a policy that gives responsibility to the manufacturers financially or physically for the treatment of consumed products that are not in use. It helps in designing products that are easier to recycle and can minimize waste. By financial responsibility, manufacturers take the cost of disposal and recycling which in turn forces manufacturers to make products easier and cheaper to recycle. By physical responsibility, producers are forced to set up take-back programs, establish collection points for each product, and partner with recycling facilities. This is a good policy that can be implemented all over the world to reduce hazardous waste [?].
- b) **Public Private Partnerships(PPP):** These are collaborative agreements between government entities and private companies that are more focused on financing, designing, and implementing projects that help the public sector. These would help in finding solutions for

many environmentally damaging issues like solar panel waste management, building zones where earthquakes can be managed effectively, and lastly lithium mining waste management. It would help by sharing knowledge and ideas across industries to improve waste management strategies [?].

- c) **Advance Seismic Monitoring:** It is a crucial strategy used in mitigating risks associated with underground earthquakes caused due to many geothermal production projects. This would play a huge role in preventing loss of property, loss of lives, and many more useful things. It would use sophisticated technology and methodologies to detect, analyze, and predict seismic activity. In today's world where AI has become a huge thing, we can use it properly for various purposes like GPS, data analysis, predictions, and many more [?].
- d) **Bio-mining with Microorganisms:** It is a technique that uses microorganisms to help in the extraction of minerals. This process is called Bioleaching, where microorganisms dissolve and separate metals from surrounding materials. It is usually used with microorganisms like *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* or *Leptospirillum ferrooxidans* which can easily oxidize minerals and release metals in a solution. It is used for the extraction of metals like gold, copper, and lithium. This method is useful as it helps reduce environmental impacts on the soil and it is also low in cost comparatively. It is flexible with scalability as it can be used on small scale like artisanal mining and large scale mining like for industrial applications [?].
- e) **Creation of Sustainable Energy and Resource Management Hub (SERMH):** It is a hub that should be created to help us integrate the economy more easily, help in improving multiple monitoring systems, and find solutions to help mitigate the impacts of renewable energy technologies. This would unite countries all over the world to help humanity in overcoming this crucial problem. Environmental Degradation, the rise of global warming, and many more problems are not just a country's problem but a global crisis. Not now but in a few years, this can cause huge damage to over world directly or indirectly. There are many benefits for this hub like we could reduce waste, minimizing the environmental footprint and we could educate local communities in sustainable agriculture and resource management. We could use new technologies like AI to better predict changes and help in data analysis. this hub could be used in promoting global sustainability and many more things which could help in growing environmental degradation [?].

These methods or techniques can be used in renewable energy projects to reduce environmental degradation and could plan for a sustainable future. These methods are very few of many more that can be implemented by private companies and governments to help us look into

Fig. 3. Bio-mining with Microorganisms

a better future.

IV. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The transition towards renewable energy has been very successful in recent years but it has also brought many disastrous activities on my Earth. And I don't think that it is going to stop soon. To overcome this issue, many new steps should be introduced for a sustainable future. From the extraction of minerals to building solar panels and new renewable energy sources could lead to soil, water, and air pollution. There are many theoretical perspectives used to structure the analysis. Some of the many are :

- a) **Life Cycle Assessment Theory(LCA):** Its main idea is to assess the environmental impacts throughout its entire life cycle, from raw materials to disposal. It is mainly used to reduce the environmental cost in the development of renewable energy projects.
- b) **Ecological Modernisation Theory:** It proposes that the development of renewable energy products can go hand in hand with environmental protection. It mainly uses newer, more advanced technologies to reduce ecological footprints. It discusses how factories or industries should manage their carbon footprint so they can also reduce some environmental pollution.
- c) **Technology Acceptance Model(TAM):** It helps in providing insights into how stakeholders perceive the environmental impacts of renewable energy project construction. It analyses how it can affect the public acceptance of renewable energy projects.

V. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND AND CURRENT RESEARCH

The topic of renewable energy has been improving day by day since the 1970s when the first fossil fuel crisis occurred. In this crisis, there were concerns about using fossil fuels due to environmental degradation. So initially, renewable energy projects were very small-scale. Then

around the 1990s-2000s, new international agreements came through which were the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement. This led to a huge increase in the development of renewable energy projects. As these grew, the awareness of this topic was all over the world. Currently, there are many steps and initiatives produced to help in reducing environmental degradation. Advancements in medical science and construction techniques brought rise to sustainable construction. Also, for some renewable energy projects, environmental justice was introduced to help humanity towards a sustainable future.

VI. GAPS IN RESEARCH

A. Degradation and Pollution from Solar Panel Coatings

Typically, solar panels are coated with a variety of harmful materials to help in enhancing their age and durability. These coatings last for around 20-30 years. Here, specifically, there has been very limited research on how the coatings might release harmful chemicals into the atmosphere. It can lead to soil pollution and contaminated groundwater, affecting all species of plants and animals. These coatings may also break down into microplastics, which could lead to microplastic pollution. It could damage the whole ecosystem. I think there should be a chemical analysis taking place that focuses on the chemicals used in these coatings. Also, new mitigation strategies should be introduced that can easily degrade these new coatings into less harmful substances. Alternatively, studies should be developed that focus on the environmental impact that could help us analyze the total impact [?].

B. Air Pollution from Geothermal Drilling

Geothermal energy is one of the widely used types of renewable energy in today's world. Its main process in harnessing energy is by drilling deep into the ground to extract heat or electricity. While geothermal has low carbon footprints it does create a lot of air pollution. The most notable gap is the release of harmful gases into the atmosphere during drilling. The specific pollutants and their impact on local air quantity, ecosystems, and human health are not well documented but it does affect these one way or another. The main pollutant released is Hydrogen Sulfide. It is present in geothermal reservoirs and can be released into the atmosphere during drilling and well testing. It is very toxic to humans and animals. It can lead to irritation of eyes, nose, and throat and also lead to severe respiratory problems. There should be a focus on monitoring and quantifying the emission produced, by using high-tech technologies. We could use advanced sensors to help us track the release of pollutants. There should also be research on regulatory and policy recommendations to help us manage and minimize air pollution from geothermal drilling. It could be done

Fig. 4. Geothermal Mining [?]

by collaborating with investors to develop guidelines to mitigate these effects [?].

C. Pollution from Renewable Energy Material Mining

Renewable energy such as solar panels, and wind turbines rely on specific materials that are found underground. These materials are usually lithium, cobalt, nickel, and other rare earth elements. While renewable energy is clean the mining process required cause environmental pollution. The focus of the current research is on the benefits of these technologies. Specifically, there is a lack of studies on the pollution generated during the mining and processing of these materials. Mining can use up a large quantity of water during the process of extracting and processing minerals. It could lead to contamination of local water supplies with toxic chemicals. Studies should be made to assess the specific pollutants that are involved in the impact on local water systems. There should be research done on recycling or safely disposing of mining waste with appropriate solutions on the matter. Conducting Environmental Impact Assessments(EIA) that encompass the full spectrum of environmental impacts. This assessment should be done on the mining regions. It would utilize a combination of field studies, laboratory analysis, and modeling to extend pollution. Also by increasing public awareness of environmental impacts to adopt corporate social responsibility(CSR) practices that prioritize environmental protection. To do this, we need to develop educational campaigns in schools and colleges and CSR initiatives that highlight the importance of sustainable mining and the role that consumers

Fig. 5. Biophilic Design [?]

and companies can play in reducing the environmental impacts of renewable energy [?].

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, while renewable energy is essential for the growth of the world and is needed for a better and sustainable future, it is crucial to acknowledge and address the environmental impacts associated with its construction. This paper shows us the harmful effects of constructing new renewable energy projects like environmental degradation. The research questions emphasize the need for more sustainable practices and technologies to help us come to a better solution towards renewable energy.

The proposed methods, such as Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), Public-Private Partnerships (PPP), advanced seismic monitoring, and biomining, offer a practical solution that can help reduce the carbon footprint of renewable energy projects. Additionally, the creation of a Sustainable Energy and Resource Management Hub (SERMH) as mentioned above in this paper could help in building new solutions by uniting global efforts to manage and minimize the environmental impacts of renewable energy. This topic should be upheld by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) which could lead to many solutions for this huge problem.

There is also much future research to explore innovative approaches, such as microbial remediation, geoengineering techniques, and biophilic design infrastructure. By focusing on sustainable construction practices and many environmental initiatives, we can achieve a cleaner and

more sustainable energy future.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

A. Use of Microbiology in renewable projects

It is an innovative approach that leverages naturally occurring or engineered microbes to break down pollutants. These microorganisms can be targeted to specific contaminants such as heavy metals, and hydrocarbons from construction material. Research should focus on how to use microorganisms to help in degrading pollutants. Certain bacteria and fungi can turn toxic substances into less harmful forms that can be easily degradable in soil. Also, some research shows that construction activities can affect soil microbiology, damaging soil ecosystems, and that they can contribute to remediation processes. This approach can be used in the construction and post-construction phases, by enhancing the natural resilience of soil ecosystems to withstand disturbance from large-scale renewable energy projects [?].

B. Biophilic Design Integration in Renewable Energy Projects

Biophilic design is an environmentally friendly approach to architecture that seeks to connect people and the built environment with nature. Applying biophilic design principles to renewable energy infrastructure presents a unique opportunity to reduce environmental impacts. Research shows that how living elements can be integrated into architectural design to help in less pollution. Use of green roofs, vertical gardens, or integrated habitats for local wildlife. Also, restoring landscape plays a major role in reducing environmental degradation by restoring areas around wind farms, and creating wetlands near geothermal plants. Its goal is to enhance local ecology while also minimizing the environmental footprint. It should also focus on human well-being, particularly in communities located near renewable energy projects. These projects then can improve community acceptance and contribute to the mental and physical health of nearby residents [?].

REFERENCES